

Salts from Tsokar Lake—I. A Study of Crystallization of Salts by Solar Evaporation

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Tsokar Lake brine was subjected to solar evaporation. Various crops obtained were characterised and mode of crystallization worked out. The probable mineralogy of the crops along with other experimental data are presented.

ADAKH district of Jammu and Kashmir state has number of saline natural lakes including Tsokar Lake (33°.15' N 33°. 2' N and 77°.5' E-78°.05' E) at an altitude of about 16000 feet above sea level and 125 kms South East of Leh having 13 sq.km area at present. The surrounding area of the lake has black soil rich in sodium, potassium and magnesium salts. There is a definite precipitated salt bed at the bottom of the lake, the thickness of which ranges from few centimeters to meters. Usually the bed salts constitute chiefly sodium sulphate but certain patches of the lake contain salts which are chiefly sodium chloride/potassium chloride, sulphate/magnesium sulphate., etc., with calcium carbonate; gypsum in traces. Specific gravity of the lake varies from 1.10 to 1.28 and in certain isolated patches of lake, sp. gr. is as high as 1.35. The Lake has two distinct regions viz. Eastern region with low sp. gr. brine (Average 1.10) and Western region with high sp. gr. brine (Average 1.28). The Lake brine is alkaline and at different places its pH ranges from 8 to 8.6. Lake remains as a frozen mass throughout the winter as temperature is said to fall up to -40° and it is only during summer months (May-Oct.) that the temperature rises appreciably and work can be done during these months when day temperature goes up to 32° or above. Experiments were conducted during summer months with Lake brine for obtaining sod. sulphate, sod. chloride, pot. sulphate, pot. chloride, magnesium sulphate, magnesium chloride and efforts are made to generalise the sequence of crystallization of salts/minerals obtained.

Experimental

500 liters of Tsokar lake brine of low density (sp. gr. 1.17; 21.8°Be) with Cl⁻=6.73%; Mg²⁺=1.31%; Na⁺=5.00%; K⁺=1.87%; B₄O₇²⁻=0.52%, was subjected to solar evaporation in a big 8'×6'×½' tray. It took 40 summer (June-Sept.) days to complete one set of experiment. Wind buffer were used besides solar radiators for increasing the evaporation rate. The radiators and buffers

were designed and fabricated by the scientists of our laboratory. Variation in Max. Min. temp. of brine and atmosphere; change in density of brine and rate of evaporation were recorded daily which are precisely presented in Table 1. The relative

TABLE 1—DENSITY VARIATION AND OTHER VARIABLES OF THE BRINE

Density n	°Be'	Total volume reduced by solar evaporation of brine	Minimum temperature of the brine before crop is collected	Crop. No. collected	Weight of the crop in kgs.
*1.177	21.8	—	—	—	—
1.164	20.3	13.4 liters	1°C	C ₁	39.0
1.171	21.2	31.2 "	2.5°C	C ₂	3.1
1.194	23.6	75.8 "	2.5°C	C ₃	14.3
1.219	26.1	57.9 "	0°C	C ₄	4.7
1.269	30.8	66.9 "	5°C	C ₅	5.0
1.279	31.7	7.7 "	3°C	C ₆	5.7
1.276	30.4	9.9 "	-2.5°C	C ₇	3.0
1.280	31.2	** "	-6°C	C ₈	1.4
1.284	32.0	** "	-6°C	C ₉	9.5
1.285	32.2	** "	-7.5°C	C ₁₀	4.3
1.289	32.6	** "	-5°C	C ₁₁	4.1
1.296	33.1	** "	-6.5°C	C ₁₂	0.5
1.305	33.9	** "	-6.5°C	C ₁₃	3.8
1.307	34.1	** "	-6.5°C	C ₁₄	4.2
1.309	34.3	** "	-5.5°C	C ₁₅	3.2
1.318	35.0	** "	-7.5°C	C ₁₆	10.0
1.319	35.1	** "	-8.5°C	C ₁₇	7.1
1.326	35.7	** "	-9°C	C ₁₈	1.0

* 500 liters of brine with 48 sq. feet surface area for evaporation.

** The volume of the brine was not measurable.

humidity varied wildly from average 3.3% to 35% which is due to drastic change in weather conditions. Daily change in brine composition (under experiment) was also recorded (Table 2). Sulphate was analysed in brine by ion exchange method (only available method on spot) which gave unsound results and so is not included in data. Analytical methods for analysis of the other ions in the brine are same as in analysis of crops. In this set of experiments 18 crops were collected and filtered

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TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF BRINE

Crop. No. collected	Ionic Composition of the Brine after collection of crops				
	%Cl ⁻	%Mg ⁺⁺	%Na ⁺	%K ⁺	%B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻
C ₁	7.25	1.58	4.36	2.10	0.56
C ₂	8.86	1.82	3.94	2.50	0.60
C ₃	9.92	1.97	4.06	2.62	0.78
C ₄	12.94	2.55	4.50	3.75	0.89
C ₅	16.31	3.16	5.62	4.50	1.24
C ₆	18.08	3.40	6.50	4.37	1.31
C ₇	18.44	3.55	7.37	4.12	1.31
C ₈	18.44	3.55	7.50	4.12	1.55
C ₉	18.79	3.82	5.66	3.37	1.55
C ₁₀	18.44	4.11	5.62	3.87	1.65
C ₁₁	18.44	4.42	4.87	3.50	1.72
C ₁₂	18.44	3.52	5.06	2.93	2.06
C ₁₃	18.79	5.69	4.37	3.25	2.20
C ₁₄	18.79	5.82	3.87	3.12	2.84
C ₁₅	18.79	6.42	3.25	3.25	3.17
C ₁₆	20.56	7.44	3.31	4.37	3.41
C ₁₇	23.49	7.83	1.00	3.75	3.61
C ₁₈	25.53	7.61	0.62	1.37	3.72

through gunny cloth instead of conical heaps¹, and allowed to drain out any brine content for 24 hours. The collected salts were air dried and analysed. The air dried crops were allowed to heat (in a platinum crucible) up to 250° in an oven for two hours and then on a Bunsen flame to red heat. The heat of flame was increased slowly. In these crops sulphate was analysed by Barium chloride method; chloride by Silver nitrate method; sodium and potassium by Flame photometer method; magnesium by EDTA method; borate by Neutralization titration method. Chemical and mineralogical composition of these crops were worked out. Various factors were taken into consideration while assigning the mineralogy to the salts which is supported by the loss on heating that tallies approximately with the calculated

theoretical water contents (Table 3) in the assigned mineralogy. In certain cases theoretical loss of the sample is more than the actual practical loss which can be attributed to overdrying of the samples (Table 3), while removing free moisture. Following sequence was adopted while assigning chemical composition to various crops.

- (1) Borate was always calculated as sodium borate.
- (2) Sulphate was represented first as magnesium sulphate; remaining sulphate as potassium sulphate and then sodium sulphate.
- (3) If enough sulphate was not available at a point then remaining magnesium was represented as magnesium chloride.
- (4) If enough or no sulphate was available at a point then sodium and potassium were represented as sodium chloride first and then potassium chloride.

Discussions

Evaporation of the brine is quite high at the initial stage which comes down after average brine density of 26-30°Be' (Table 1). In this quick evaporation the main salts separated out is chiefly sodium sulphate. The increase in the concentration of chloride, magnesium, and borate ions, with solar evaporation (Table 2) shows the concentration of brine with respect to magnesium chloride and sodium borate. Chemical composition assigned to various crops has been plotted (Fig. 1) against concentration of the brine. As is clear from the Fig. 1 that sodium chloride is continuously supersaturated out of the brine and maximum reaches in the density

TABLE 3—IONIC COMPOSITION OF SALTS SEPARATED

Crop No.	%Cl ⁻	%Mg ⁺⁺	%Na ⁺	%K ⁺	%B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻	%SO ₄ ²⁻	Loss on heating	Total	Theoretical (calculated) water content in the assigned mineralogy (Ref. Table 5).
C ₁	2.57	0.48	29.70	1.75	0.28	62.30	2.94	100.02	2.46
C ₂	2.66	0.52	28.84	2.00	0.27	60.91	4.75	99.95	2.25
C ₃	4.43	1.07	28.56	2.00	0.47	60.01	3.47	100.01	3.60*
C ₄	5.85	1.75	23.94	4.00	0.53	53.54	10.51	100.12	8.50
C ₅	4.63	5.96	3.10	16.25	0.32	43.43	26.35	100.09	26.85*
C ₆	18.98	4.44	11.30	14.00	0.22	32.56	18.60	100.05	19.97*
C ₇	29.41	3.32	19.10	9.75	0.78	25.07	13.29	100.12	13.67*
C ₈	26.01	3.99	15.46	10.25	0.60	25.46	13.36	100.13	18.34
C ₉	33.35	2.32	21.78	8.65	0.62	19.78	13.55	100.05	7.18
C ₁₀	43.87	1.32	21.07	14.40	0.60	7.18	11.58	100.02	11.03
C ₁₁	54.48	0.73	28.65	10.25	0.31	1.19	4.54	100.13	3.94
C ₁₂	51.41	1.26	25.39	12.50	0.47	3.51	5.49	100.03	4.93
C ₁₃	36.55	4.28	17.95	9.75	0.78	16.42	14.32	100.05	10.64
C ₁₄	49.41	1.80	23.18	12.35	0.58	3.86	8.83	100.01	7.91
C ₁₅	43.94	2.92	22.50	8.50	0.70	9.09	12.38	100.03	13.79*
C ₁₆	19.79	6.32	9.18	6.50	0.60	24.95	32.70	100.04	33.45*
C ₁₇	24.91	6.32	7.15	8.00	0.89	20.55	31.99	99.91	34.63*
C ₁₈	23.08	8.27	4.46	4.75	1.55	8.87	44.10	100.08	39.03

* Overdried samples.

Fig. 1.

range of 1.27 (30.9°Be) to 1.32 (35°Be) and about 73% pure sodium chloride comes out at 1.289 (32.6°Be). There are distinct ranges in density 1.22 (26.2°Be) to 1.285 (32.2°Be) and 1.28 (31.8°Be) to 1.34 (36.8°Be) when potassium sulphate and potassium chloride are separated out of the brine respectively. Within their respective ranges, pot. sulphate separates out maximum at 1.27 (30.9°Be) and pot. chloride at 1.295-1.30 (31.1-33.5°Be) and also maximum of picromite ($K_2SO_4 \cdot MgSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$) and silvinite ($NaCl \cdot KCl$) is separated out at these densities respectively (Table 4). Magnesium sulphate in various crops, is found in various forms and has all possible water molecules with it, viz. epsomite ($MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$), magnesium sulphate hexahydrate ($MgSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$), kiserite ($MgSO_4 \cdot H_2O$) and also anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Magnesium sulphate is separated out continuously throughout the crystallization and shows two distinct peaks (Fig. 1) at 1.27 (30.9°Be) and 1.317 (34.92°Be).

In these experiments the fractional evaporation shows distinctly four regions in crystallization viz.

TABLE 4—PROBABLE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SEPARATED SALTS

Crop No.	Na_2SO_4	K_2SO_4	$MgSO_4$	KCl	NaCl	$MgCl_2$	$Na_2B_4O_7$
C ₁	86.58	3.90	2.37	—	4.23	—	0.36
C ₂	83.45	4.45	2.57	—	4.38	—	0.35
C ₃	78.87	4.46	5.40	—	7.30	—	0.61
C ₄	61.71	8.91	8.66	—	9.64	—	0.69
C ₅	—	36.20	29.49	—	7.68	—	0.42
C ₆	—	27.27	21.97	3.36	28.57	—	0.28
C ₇	—	21.72	16.42	—	48.46	—	0.23
C ₈	—	22.82	16.08	—	38.66	3.43	0.78
C ₉	—	3.57	6.53	24.42	53.14	—	0.78
C ₁₀	—	19.27	11.48	—	54.95	—	0.80
C ₁₁	—	—	1.50	19.43	72.63	1.65	0.40
C ₁₂	—	—	4.40	23.84	64.24	1.45	0.61
C ₁₃	—	—	20.58	13.60	45.07	0.47	0.97
C ₁₄	—	—	4.84	23.55	58.53	3.51	0.75
C ₁₅	—	—	11.39	16.22	56.70	2.43	0.91
C ₁₆	—	—	31.27	12.40	22.89	—	0.78
C ₁₇	—	—	25.88	15.26	17.53	8.10	1.15
C ₁₈	—	—	11.12	9.06	10.18	23.61	2.01

Mirabilite $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$, Picromerte $K_2SO_4 \cdot MgSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, Silvinite $NaCl \cdot KCl$, Bischofite $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. Since the temperature of the brine never rises above 30° as sodium sulphate will always crystallize out as mirabilite² (Glaur's Salt; $NaSO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$). In our experiments the Glaur's salt on air drying gets converted into thenardite (anhydrous sodium sulphate). Sodium sulphate (Mirabilite) is chiefly separated out of the brine in the density range of 1.17 (21.9°Be) to 1.219 (26.1°Be), picromerte in the density range of 1.194 (23.6°Be) to 1.284 (32°Be), silvinite in the density range of 1.284 (32°Be) to 1.3187 (35°Be) followed by bischofite after (35°Be). All these minerals are always contaminated with other salts. Kainite and carnallite type of salts are also separated out along with silvinite in the density range of 32.5-34°Be (Table 5).

TABLE 5—PROBABLE MINERALOGY OF THE SEPARATED SALTS

Crop No.	Thenardite Na_2SO_4	Arca-nite K_2SO_4	Scheonite (picromerte) $K_2SO_4 \cdot MgSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$	Halite $NaCl$	Silvinite $NaCl \cdot KCl$	Kainite $KCl \cdot MgSO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$	Carnallite $KCl \cdot MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	Bischofite $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	Sodium Borate decahydrate $Na_2B_4O_7 \cdot 10H_2O$	Magnesium Sulphate $MgSO_4$	Remarks (Probable state of the Magnesium Sulphate)
C ₁	86.58	0.47	7.93	4.23	—	—	—	—	0.68	—	—
C ₂	83.45	0.73	7.23	4.38	—	—	—	—	0.66	—	—
C ₃	78.87	—	11.48	7.30	—	—	—	—	1.15	1.42	$MgSO_4$ is as anhydrous
C ₄	61.71	—	20.75	9.64	—	—	—	—	1.31	2.15	$MgSO_4$ is as epsomite
C ₅	—	—	33.65	7.63	—	—	—	—	0.79	4.49	$MgSO_4$ is as epsomite
C ₆	—	—	33.00	25.93	6.00	—	—	—	0.53	3.14	$MgSO_4$ is as epsomite
C ₇	—	—	59.19	48.46	—	—	—	—	0.43	1.42	$MgSO_4$ is as anhydrous
C ₈	—	—	52.74	38.66	—	—	—	7.32	1.47	0.32	$MgSO_4$ is as anhydrous
C ₉	—	—	8.24	33.99	43.57	—	—	—	1.48	4.07	$MgSO_4$ is as heptahydrate
C ₁₀	—	2.64	36.42	54.95	—	—	—	—	1.52	—	—
C ₁₁	—	—	—	57.39	34.67	—	—	3.52	0.76	1.50	$MgSO_4$ is as heptahydrate
C ₁₂	—	—	—	50.70	30.80	12.58	4.22	—	1.17	—	—
C ₁₃	—	—	—	40.78	9.76	42.58	1.37	—	1.34	—	—
C ₁₄	—	—	—	40.07	42.01	—	—	5.68	1.42	4.84	$MgSO_4$ is as heptahydrate
C ₁₅	—	—	—	43.97	28.95	—	—	5.18	1.72	11.39	$MgSO_4$ is as epsomite
C ₁₆	—	—	—	13.17	22.12	—	—	—	1.48	31.27	$MgSO_4$ is as epsomite
C ₁₇	—	—	—	5.56	27.23	—	—	17.28	2.18	25.88	$MgSO_4$ is as kiserite
C ₁₈	—	—	—	8.07	15.17	—	—	49.23	3.77	11.12	$MgSO_4$ is as heptahydrate

In the sets of experiments conducted in the field it was found that after recovering sodium sulphate the brine can be allowed to evaporate up to density of 32°Be to recover picromite type of salts ; and hereafter it can be allowed to evaporate upto density of 35-36°Be when we get mixed salts which can be subjected to various processing for the recovery of individual salt/mineral. After 36° Be the brine contains chiefly magnesium chloride (sodium and potassium ions concentration is quite low) which also can be subjected to drying and purification for obtaining pure magnesium chloride. The work regarding extraction of various individual salts by geothermal energy at Puga valley (Ladakh) will be communicated soon.

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